

Poster Presentation Number 63, Session 3, Friday 2:00-3:00 pm

The late Middle Palaeolithic occupation of Abri du Maras (layer 1, Neronian, southeast France): integrating lithic analyses, ZooMS and radiocarbon dating to reconstruct Neanderthal hunting behaviour

Karen Ruebens¹, Virginie Sinet-Mathiot¹, Sahra Talamo^{1,2}, Geoff M Smith¹, Frido Welker^{1,3}, Jean-Jacques Hublin¹, Shannon McPherron¹

1 - Department of Human Evolution, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Deutscher Platz 6, 04103 Leipzig, Germany · 2 - Department of Chemistry G. Ciamician, Alma Mater Studiorum, University of Bologna Via Selmi 2, Bologna, 40126, Italy · 3 - Section for Evolutionary Genomics, GLOBE Institute, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

The exact mechanisms and dynamics of Neanderthal hunting behaviour (including prey acquisition methods and weapon technologies) remain difficult to reconstruct and continue to form a topic of debate [1]. Identifying stone-tipped hunting weapons in the archaeological record is obscured by various methodological issues [2] and in general lithic points are sparse across the European Middle Palaeolithic record. An exception is the Neronian entity in southeast France, characterised by ventrally retouched Soyons points [3]. One of the largest Neronian assemblages is layer 1 at Abri du Maras (>3,000 lithics), excavated by Gilles between 1946 and 1950 [4] and by Combier in 1958 and 1963 [5]. This study contextualises the layer 1 lithic and faunal archives to gain a better understanding of site formation, chronology, assemblage integrity and patterns of Neanderthal hunting behaviour.

The focus of our lithic analyses was on recording attributes that have been described as indicative of projectile use or hafting such as macro-traces of use (e.g., breakage patterns at the tip and macroscopic edge damage) and modifications near the proximal end of the point (e.g., basal retouch and ventral thinning). We applied this focused attribute analysis to flakes, blades and points from the Gilles collection to contextualise the morphometric and technological characteristics of the Soyons points. We found that these points were made on a variety of blank types (including Levallois, laminar and discoidal flaking techniques) and ventral retouch is present across different artefact types (including points, scrapers and denticulates). Next, we collected similar typo-technological data on a sample of blanks from the recently excavated and well-contextualised point-rich layer 4.1 of Abri du Maras (MIS-3). Although macrofractures are present, other modifications related to the use of the points as projectile tips are rare and detailed edge damage studies were obscured by the preservation state of the artefacts, with many of them being heavily desilicified.

To further assess the human behaviour at the site, Zooarchaeology by Mass Spectrometry (ZooMS) was applied to all unidentifiable fragments larger than 25mm (n: 278) from both the Gilles and Combier layer 1 collections. The resulting faunal spectrum is diverse with significant proportions of equidae, Bos/Bison, cervids and reindeer. Carnivore remains and modifications are absent while human modifications are present across species. We selected eleven bones for radiocarbon dating and five had sufficient collagen yields but returned dates younger than expected (ranging from 39,000 to 29,000 calBP). Together with an assessment of the glutamine deamidation values of the ZooMS faunal specimens, we discuss the integrity of the layer 1 material.

Finally, we place both the lithic and faunal material from Abri du Maras layer 1 in its broader regional context and discuss its relation to other Neronian assemblages and more general problematics related to studying material from old excavations. Overall, our analyses show that while we managed to obtain additional behavioural data from the Maras layer 1 collections, we also encountered contextual issues that require caution when making interpretations of Neanderthal behaviour within these upper layers.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 745662. We would like to thank Patricia Guillermin and Robin Furestier from the Grand Site de France de l'Aven d'Orgnac for access to the Abri du Maras layer 1 material.

References: [1] Gaudzinski-Windheuser, S., 2016. Hunting lesions in Pleistocene and early Holocene European bone assemblages and their implications for our knowledge on the use and timing of lithic projectile technology. In: R. Iovita & K. Sano (Eds.), *Multidisciplinary approaches to the study of stone age weaponry* (pp. 77–100). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. [2] Rots, V., & Plisson, H., 2014. Projectiles and the abuse of the use-wear method in a search for impact. *J of Arch. Science*, 48, 154-165. [3] Slimak, L., 2008. The Neronian and the historical structure of cultural shifts from Middle to Upper Palaeolithic in Mediterranean France. *J of Arch. Science* 35, 2204-2214. [4] Baudet, J. L. Barthès, J., Bouchud, P. et al., 1955. L'abri du Maras (Saint-Martin-d'Ardèche). *Revue archéologique* 45, 1-16. [5] Combier, J., 1967. Le Paléolithique de l'Ardèche dans son cadre paléoclimatique. Publication de l'Institut de Préhistoire de l'Université de Bordeaux, Delmas édit., n° 4, 462 p.